

Educating the Whole Child in a Child with Special Needs: What we know and understand & what we can do

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What do we know and understand when we say 'educate the whole child?' According to Noddings (2005), most of the time, we mean "to accomplish academic goals with the task of pursuing the physical, moral, social, emotional, spiritual, and aesthetic aims that we associate with the *whole child*" (p.30). What do we mean the *whole child*? Any child is a *whole* person – not a mere collection of attributes, some to be addressed in one place, and others to be addressed elsewhere. What if a child has some special needs? Is he/she still considered *whole* or *less-than-whole* as an individual? Can we still educate the whole child with special needs? While there are more questions we can ask than answer them, in this article, I shall attempt to address the last question though there is no one straight forward answer to it.

When we as educators "recognize that children are *whole* individuals, the temptation arises to describe the *whole* in terms of collective parts and to make sure

that every aspect, part, or attribute is somehow 'covered' in the curriculum" (Noddings, 2005, p.31). Let me illustrate what I mean by that. When we consider children as moral beings, we must provide them character education program. If they are artistically or musically inclined, we provide them arts classes. When their physical fitness is on the decline and many have become obese, physical education as well as nutrition classes is strictly observed and implemented. What happens next? In no time, we begin to complain that our curriculum is overloaded!

If we say that schools and other social institutions bear the responsibility for nurturing the *whole child*, we must recognize that different institutions will have different emphases. Schools will take greater responsibility for teaching the four R's; medical clinics, polyclinics and hospitals for health checkups and vaccinations; families for food, shelter, clothing and up-bringing; and places of worship for spiritual instruction and enlightenment. No institution on its own is able to completely meet the needs of the *whole child*, but a collaborative effort of various social institutions will stand a better chance in achieving it.

However, the needs of a child cannot be rigidly compartmentalized. The massive human problems of any society demand a holistic treatment. For instance, medical clinics and hospitals in the United States are working with lawyers, social workers and insurance agents to improve better health services for both adults and children (Shipler, 2004). We know that healthy families do much more than just feed and clothe their children; good

parenting is not to be neglected if we want our children to grow up to become respectable members in our community (Flick, 1996). Similarly, schools must be concerned with the total development of children under their charge (Noddings, 2005).

How do we go about educating the whole child?

Let us first of all look at the normal child – the whole normal child – and by this, I mean the child has no medical ailments or learning disabilities of any kind. Such a child is the dream of every parent: intelligent, healthy, diligent, well-behaved, and so on ... a perfect individual! However, we must not forget that not every child is wholly normal. Like everyone else, a child has his/her own strengths and weaknesses. A child with an average academic performance is described as normal or simply, able, while a gifted or talented child is considered to be highly-able. However, a child with mental retardation is seen as disabled, who can be either an educable or a trainable disabled. Then there are also those slow learners whom we look upon as less-able. What do these terms “highly-able”, “able”, “less-able” and “disabled” mean to us as educators when we talk about educating the whole child?

The fundamental role in educating the whole child regardless of his/her ability, as I see it, is to ensure that the child undergoes proper personal and social development by promoting self-awareness, self-esteem (which includes various self-concepts), relationship with others, independence, and social responsibility in him/her (Cramer, 1998; Duck, 1994). The reasons for this personal and social development above all the other areas of development are twofold. Firstly, the child’s development as a whole person living in this society is the utmost concern of any educator. Secondly, it sets as the platform for educators to promote other types of learning. While the former concerns about maximizing the potential of any child (highly-able, able, less-able or disabled) as a learner so that the child can grow up to become a good and useful citizen, the latter focuses on learning as a life-long process. It is the latter that I am more interested. Our clear understanding of the learning process is the first step to know how best and what we can do to educate the highly-able, able, less-able or disabled child as much as he/she can learn or be trained as a whole or complete person. In this way, the child’s potential/ performance is stretched to the best of his/her ability.

Figure 1: The Learning Process

What do we understand about the process of learning?

To know how a child learns, we need to know and understand what learning is all about. A lot has already been written and published in literature (e.g., Halford, 1993; Skinner, 1965) on the various theories and models of learning and in this article I shall not delve on them. I would define in simple terms learning as a life-long and life-span developmental process that involves several levels of sub-processes simultaneously and sequentially, moving gradually towards formal instruction (see Figure 1).

When a toddler learns, learning is seen as 'caught' where very little effort is needed to teach him/her. As the toddler grows older, learning is no longer a spontaneous process. Teaching has to come in and learning becomes a deliberate process. In this instance, we say learning is 'taught.' Many educators believe that there is this critical or sensitive period when a child learns best between 2 and 5 years of age, and thereafter, the learning performance starts to slow down (Santrock, 1995).

At the first level, learning is a sensory-motor process involving our five senses – auditory (ears), visual (eyes), haptic (skin), olfactory (nose) and gustatory (tongue) – in addition to the motor process (gross and fine motor skills).

- Learning as an auditory process can be divided further into aural sub-process and oral sub-process. The former involves hearing (receiving auditory input but not necessarily registering in the mind) and listening (careful reception and registration of auditory input). The latter involves talking (chatting without thinking through) and speaking (thinking before saying anything).
- Learning as a visual process involves what we observe (paying attention to details) in our surrounding and later how we perceive based on our interpretation of our observation.

- Learning is a haptic process involving touch (tactile) but it also includes proprioceptive sense, which is the correlation of unconscious sensations from the skin and joints that allows conscious appreciation of the position of the body. For young children, an awareness of oneself (e.g., body) is an essential step in knowing one's physical self before venturing out into the external world.
- Learning as an olfactory process involves smell which plays an important role in sensing out food or alerting us to some danger lurking around. Scent is one learning process a young child acquires early in life to identify his/her mother.
- Learning as a gustatory process involves eating (gobbling food) and tasting (savoring food). Young children learn about new objects such as toys by putting them in their mouth to bite or taste.

When motor skills are added to each of these sub-processes of the sensory process of learning, we have learning as a sensory-motor process in the following ways ... as

- an auditory-motor process (e.g., as in dictation and spelling, listening comprehension);
- a visual-motor process (e.g., as in completing tessellations, handwriting);
- a haptic-motor process, also known as kinesthetic-tactile process (e.g., as in physical education);
- an olfactory-motor process (e.g., as in a chemistry experiment to find out if ammonia is present since it gives a pungent smell); and
- a gustatory-motor process (e.g., as in a cookery class to taste if the soup in preparation is plain or too salty).

At the second level, learning is an adaptive behavioral process which represents the conceptual (e.g., receptive and expressive languages, reading and writing), social

(e.g., responsibility, interpersonal interaction) and practical (e.g., dressing, eating, toileting) skills that a child has to learn in order to be able to function in his/her daily life. Significant limitations in adaptive behavior may impact one's daily life and affect the ability to respond to a particular situation or environment.

At the third level, learning is also an affective process as the child grows up not only interacting with his/her parents alone but also with others such as cousins, friends and even strangers (Holden, 1997). Socio-emotional relationships with others are constantly being established, changed and/or broken by the child as his/her social circle evolves over time (Hinde, 1987). It is during this process of learning that a child finds out what, who and how he/she learns best with someone – normally an adult (e.g., a childcare teacher) – whom he/she knows, understands and trusts. Only then is the child more willing to be taught (rather than being compelled) to read, write and count ... and as the child grows older he/she learns even more, such as to love, to get attached and so on (Karen, 1998).

As the child grows older or goes to a primary school, formal education comes in. At the next or fifth level, learning is now more of a cognitive process: learning to sing, read, spell, and write; learning to count and problem-solve; learning to pay attention in class during lesson; learning to ... the list goes on. A good concept formation (e.g., addition and subtraction) is best achieved if teaching is properly carried out in the way that best suits the child's cognitive learning needs and style. However, in a regular classroom where the number of children is large, there will be several of those who are unable to follow instructions or fail to understand what has been taught. There is a need to understand such children and their learning difficulties if a teacher hopes to educate them as whole beings or learners. The Learning Support Program is one example of how the mainstream education system is coping to educate the whole child with

special needs so that he/she can learn and acquire the necessary knowledge and skills needed to succeed in studies. In another instance, the subject-based banding (i.e., foundation, standard and higher levels) system that the Ministry of Education is implementing in primary schools is yet another good attempt to educate the whole child according to his/her level of ability (aptitude) to perform well in different subjects so that the child's potential can be maximized.

At a higher level, learning is more than just a cognitive process. It is also a meta-cognitive process which concerns the child's understanding of what he/she is learning and it also includes self-monitoring of his/her progress in learning (Goswami, 1998).

How to help a child with special needs to learn as a whole child?

Learning, as we can see, is a complex process with several sub-processes consisting of many different skills and it takes place sequentially and simultaneously. Anything can happen at any point during the process of learning resulting in all kinds of learning problems or difficulties.

Every academic activity a child participates in class requires strong, efficient underlying learning skills if it is to be accomplished successfully (Brown, 2000). Many children become frustrated and find schoolwork difficult because they do not have the learning skills and strategies required to process information properly. For these children, any additional school/homework, or special attention not specifically addressing the underlying learning skill weakness, will only intensify their learning problems or difficulties and compound their frustration.

Learning skills are developed through the following stages (see Figure 2).

At the foundational level, learning builds on a child's innate abilities which are inherited

Figure 2: Developmental Stages of Learning Skills

and genetically coded at birth. Very few children can learn anywhere near their maximum capacity as established by their innate skills. This is why both study and practice rewards most children with significant progress made in learning and performance. The flow of their learning development progresses through the stages of sensory-motor skills, affective (socio-emotional) skills, cognitive skills, and finally results in their ability to assimilate formal instruction in a regular classroom situation. A deficiency in any one stage can result in problems in the subsequent dependent stages.

While our schools continue to focus on academic instruction, they seldom recognize that not all children possess the fundamental learning skills required to efficiently process and understand information presented through academic instruction. Without the appropriate level(s) of learning skills in place, increased academic instruction and remedial lessons can do nothing to improve a child's learning ability. In fact, little is accomplished to help these children learn, and hence, the failure to educate them as whole individual learners. Low self-esteem sets in and maladaptive behavior begins to manifest itself in the

child concerned. Soon, off-task behavior and misbehavior become a frequent issue of concern to be reckoned with by both teachers in class and parents at home (Sarason & Sarason, 1998). Let us take a closer look at each stage of learning skills and should there be any deficiency, to recommend appropriate actions to be taken so as to educate the whole child in the child with special needs.

- **Innate Abilities**

At the foundation of the learning process are a child's innate or genetically determined abilities. His/Her upward ceiling in performance is defined by innate abilities, but how near the child comes to performing at those upper limits is determined by other elements (e.g., interest and motivation) necessary to learning (Franken, 2002). It is these innate abilities that a child is assessed (e.g., an IQ test) to determine if he/she is highly-able, able, less-able or disabled in his/her performance as a learner.

- **Sensory-Motor Skills**

The sensory-motor process of learning is developed on the foundation of the child's innate abilities. It covers sensory and motor skills which are partially

determined by genetic code and partly acquired through repeated interaction with the environment. Such skills can be improved with proper practice. Sensory skills refer to those such as vision, hearing, touch, smell and taste. They are most essential for receiving information. Motor skills relate to muscles and movement, and include crawling, walking, running, handwriting and speaking. Motor skills give expression to the information our senses receive and process. Should there be any deficiency in any of these skills, the intervention program which includes sensory integration therapy, occupational therapy and/or physical therapy is often recommended.

- **Adaptive-Behavioral Skills**

The adaptive-behavioral process of learning refers to "the effectiveness or degree with which an individual meets the standards of personal independence and social responsibility expected of his/her age and social group" (Grossman, 1973, p.11). It covers a wide range of skills at different stages of development. During infancy and early childhood, the adaptive-behavioral process of learning covers sensory-motor skills (covered earlier; see above), communication skills (speech and language), self-help skills and socialization skills (interacting and getting along with others). During the late childhood and early adolescence, it covers application of basic academic skills in everyday life activities, application of appropriate reasoning and judgment in mastery of the environment, and social skills (participation in group activities and interpersonal relationships). Finally, during late adolescence and adulthood, it concerns vocational and social responsibility and performance. Children with adaptive-behavioral deficits can be helped through applied behavior analysis that involves systematically arranging environmental events to produce desired changes in their behavior.

- **Affective (Socio-emotional) Skills**

The affective process of learning is concerned with good "people skills" (e.g., interpersonal and communication skills). According to Kratliwohl, Bloom, and Masa (1964), the affective domain encompasses qualities that are prerequisites for socially acceptable behaviors in children, such as desirable interests, attitudes, values, and character development (including self-esteem and self-image). Learning in the affective domain is often challenging because of its subjective nature. Unlike sensory-motor and cognitive skills that can be evaluated by written examination or practical testing, affective/behavioral skills are difficult to identify, quantify, and assess. Intervention approaches to remedy deficits in this area of concern include social skill training, behavior modification, play therapy and counseling.

- **Cognitive Skills**

The cognitive process of learning allows children to process the sensory information they receive. These include their ability to analyze, evaluate, retain information, recall experiences, make comparisons and determine action (Giles, 2005). Although learning as a cognitive process has an innate component, its bulk of cognitive skills are learned or deliberately acquired (e.g., by being taught). When this development fails to take place naturally, cognitive weaknesses are the result and they diminish a child's ability to learn, and are difficult to correct without specific and suitable intervention. Cognitive skills can be practiced and improved with the right teaching. Using the appropriate therapy (e.g., special needs or educational therapy and remedial teaching), the brain of a struggling learner can actually be "rewired" and cognitive function can be restored or enhanced (Goswami, 1998). While weak cognitive skills can be strengthened, normal cognitive skills can be enhanced to increase ease and

performance in learning. That is why enrichment programs (e.g., abacus, phonics, speech and drama) offered outside the regular school system still play an important role in educating the whole child.

• Formal Instruction

When we talk about formal instruction, it includes academic subjects (e.g., algebra and reading) that are dependent on the strength of a child's underlying learning skills if these subjects are to be acquired successfully and easily. While the knowledge base of each academic subject can be expanded, without the proper foundation of earlier learning skills, academic progress can be a difficult and frustrating challenge, especially to a child with special needs. Remedial teaching and intensive private tuition may become necessary to help these children to cope with their learning.

Concluding Remarks

Let us go back to our question posed at the beginning of this article: Can we educate the whole child in a child with special needs? While the answer is not a complete yes, it can still be done, depending on our experience and training, and involving more effort on our part to remedy the deficits at different developmental stages of learning skills. Until we have a clearer understanding of what a whole child means in a child with special needs, any attempt to integrate children with special needs into the mainstream education system might meet with difficulties and even disappointment. However, this does not mean that integration of children with special needs in regular schools is not possible, just that we need to do more homework before implementing such an educational initiative. Perhaps at this moment, what we ought to do is to reach out to parents of children with special needs. They are the people, who need to be educated first, especially to accept their exceptional children as who they are

and to seek early intervention as soon as possible rather than remaining in a state of denial or going round to seek miraculous cures which are not even there.

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